

Promoting Open Science Through Collaborative Learning. The MOOC “Science 2.0 and Open Research Methods”

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ABSTRACT

Keywords

Open Science, MOOC, Higher Education, Open Research

Purpose of this paper

This paper examines the MOVING MOOC “Science 2.0 and open research methods”, an online course for open science developed and conducted at the Media Centre at TU Dresden. The MOOC (massive open online course) is intended to fill a current gap in the scientific methods training for young scholars in institutions of higher education. Digitization and the international and interdisciplinary opening of science in the 21st century require a new set of meta-competencies for young researchers to thrive in this environment. Scientific Communication and collaboration are depending more and more on digital tools and online environments. The term Science 2.0 refers to the targeted use of social media, participative web technologies and online communities in scientific practice. Science 2.0 is closely linked to the concept of Open Science, which aims to remove barriers that restrict access to scientific data and knowledge.

In the MOOC, young scientists get an introduction to open research methods and learn to use social web technologies and online communities as research tools: to build networks, discuss findings and collaborate with scientists across disciplinary, cultural and geographical

boundaries. Open Science means the opening of scientific research processes facilitated by digitization and the proliferation of social web technologies. It is an umbrella term that encompasses technological, pragmatic and normative dimensions (Fecher & Friesike 2014). New research infrastructures like the European Open Science Cloud¹ or the Open Science Framework² are being created to support researchers in information discovery, scientific collaboration and communication and in sharing their research outputs early and openly. Making science more open and collaborative has far reaching implications for the whole research cycle: from generating ideas, collecting data and collaborating in research teams to publishing research papers or other research products like code, data and methods. Social technologies such as blogs, wikis and social bookmarking services in combination with movements such as Creative Commons offer completely new opportunities to publish, share, discuss and reproduce scientific findings and data. And movements such as Open Data, Open Access or Open Educational Resources regard free access to knowledge as a normative prerequisite for the development of humanity and question the institutional power of profit-oriented publishers for scientific journals and data, which often keep research results behind a paywall.

However, despite the many advantages that digital technologies and open research workflows provide for researchers (see McKiernan et al. 2016) scholars are hesitant to share their research and data early and open their workflows to others. The reason for this reluctance is usually not a general rejection of the concept of open science, but a sense of ambiguity about what exactly open research means and also a lack of skills and competences to effectively use digital tools and collaborative methods. Therefore, training researchers in open research methods and open science workflows is key for the proliferation of open science practices.

Design/methodology/approach

The MOVING MOOC “Science 2.0 and open research methods” is designed as a four-week crash course to give learners a broad overview on open collaborative science³. In the context of the MOOC, both didactic elements of cMOOCs and xMOOCs were used. In xMOOCs, knowledge is conveyed in the classical sense with the help of clearly structured learning content

¹ European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). <https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=open-science-cloud>

² OSF Open Science Framework. <https://osf.io/>

³ <https://moving.mz.tu-dresden.de/mooc>

such as videos, quizzes and PDF documents within individual learning sequences, which are in the tradition of cognitive learning theories. In this form of MOOCs, the course takes place over a period of several weeks according to a previously defined course plan. At the end of an xMOOC, a formative assessment is usually carried out, e.g. in the form of an online test. If the assessment is successfully passed, the xMOOC participants receive a certificate of achievement (see Schulmeister 2005). The cMOOCs ("connectivist" MOOCs), on the other hand, focus on collaborative learning. According to the learning theory of connectivism coined by George Siemens and Stephen Downes (Downes 2012), learning takes place in networks and self-organized by the participants. Teachers take on the role of moderators, facilitate various learning paths and provide corresponding learning content. What and how they learn is decided by the learners in a collaborative exchange (Haug & Wedekind 2013). The MOOC participants in cMOOCs learn in the group through collaboration and exchange with other participants, for example by writing and commenting on blog posts or jointly creating content. Learning becomes a collaborative experience, learners and digital artefacts remain connected in a network (Staubitz et. al. 2015).

For the MOOC "Science 2.0 and open research methods", elements of both cMOOCs and xMOOCs were used. The MOOC topics, open science and open research methods, already imply the great importance of networking and community building. In this respect, connectivist MOOC elements that promote communication and collaboration play a special role. In the sense of an "open science practice", the participants should actively test the use of digital tools for communication and collaboration and exchange their experiences with other participants and reflect on their use of these tools. In the MOOC this is achieved via moderated forums and the use of social media. At the same time, xMOOC elements, i.e. videos, infographics or literature, are used to convey basic knowledge about Open Science as well as attitudes and competencies associated with it. Participants do not have to follow a uniformly defined learning path, but can decide for themselves which of the resources they want to use and which thematic focuses they want to set.

Findings/expected Findings

In already three live runs the MOOC "Science 2.0 and open research methods" attracted more than 500 learners from different academic disciplines and professional backgrounds. Each week is covering one of four main topics: (1) What is open science, what are the main aspects and why should scholars care; (2) how have digital tools and platforms changed the information landscape and the way to do research; (3) how has open science changed scholarly communication and collaboration; and (4) how can scientists make their own research more

open? The MOOC is addressing young scholars (PhDs and PostDocs) who were already working in an academic environment, so we designed the course in a way that their everyday work experience as researchers was integrated in the learning approach.

Each week there are six to eleven activities that the students engage with in the course. The course material is provided in a variety of media formats (texts, blogs, videos, audio, infographics, etc.) and is based on reused, re-compiled and self-produced Open Educational Resources (OER).

The activities in the MOOC differ in duration, activation level, format and learning objective. Learning materials are provided in different formats: Videos are used to give an overview of a topic, give testimonials or show transfer possibilities for what has been learnt into one's own practice. Infographics help to give an overview of a topic or explain complex procedures and concrete workflows. Texts, like journal articles and handbook chapters, served the deepening of knowledge. Blogs and podcasts illuminate the weekly topics from a more personal perspective of scholars and other practitioners. In small weekly assignments, learners are encouraged to try out open scientific practices such as crowdsourcing academic tasks via social networks like Twitter⁴ and Reddit⁵, using open repositories (Zenodo⁶, Figshare⁷, OSF, etc.) to share their research, using open licenses like Creative Commons, or creating a personal ORCID⁸. Part of each live run of the MOOC was also a webinar in which learners had the chance to ask questions and discuss challenges and benefits of Open Science with invited experts on the topic and the course moderators.

Practical implications

Evaluations showed that for many learners the MOOC “Science 2.0 and open research methods” was the first time they systematically engaged with open science topics and for many of them this experience was transformative in the way they planned to approach openness in academic workflows in the future. Many of them enjoyed the collaborative format, the diversity of learning materials and media formats and they actively engaged with their peers in the forums. The advantage of MOOCs as a learning format is that they – other than face-to-face training or workshops - facilitate a large number of learners at once. The online format makes it possible that learners can participate in the course from anywhere they are – from their workplace, from home or their universities. With the exception of the live webinar, the course is asynchronous so

⁴ <https://twitter.com/>

⁵ <https://www.reddit.com/r/askscience/>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/>

⁷ <https://figshare.com/>

⁸ <https://orcid.org/>

that learners can decide when to engage with the learning materials, when to take part in the forum discussions and complete their assignments. This flexibility was highly appreciated by the participants because it allowed them to engage in the course on their own pace and e.g. use spare time during their work day or off-time for learning. At the same time, learners enjoy the social learning aspects of the MOOC. Other than in self-paced online courses, learner felt to be part of a larger community by actively engaging with their peers and learning from the exchange among each other. The MOOC is designed as roadmap course of Open Science to give learners a broad overview of major aspects of open research in a limited amount of time. Keeping the course relatively short had the benefit of having lower drop-out rates, but it also meant that subjects often could not be dealt with in depth. Some learners were interested in additional modules (discipline specific or topical) and asked for more specialized open science training.

Feedback also shows that many of the participants planned to integrate open research methods in their work routines or even started open science initiatives in their work environment and at home institutions after the course was finished - an outcome that the creators of the MOOC had intended and hoped for.

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